

INFLUENCE OF TEMPERATURE ON THE DURABILITY OF POLYMER COMPOSITE SYSTEMS

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SUMMARY: An innovative approach to the temperature dependence of polymer-based systems was used in the present paper. An engineering model was developed that can describe the modulus versus temperature behavior of any polymer (thermoset, thermoplastic, amorphous, semi-crystalline, low/high molecular weight...) from the glassy state to the flow region. This model was applied to neat polyphenylene sulfide (PPS) and successfully integrated into a micromechanics model (compression) that describes the behavior of unidirectional AS4/PPS composite in end-loaded bending. Finally, the importance of this approach for durability tools was illustrated by integrating the stiffness-temperature polymer model into a life prediction code called MRLife to predict the life of a unidirectional carbon fiber polymer matrix composite under combined thermal and mechanical loads.

KEYWORDS: Durability, PMC, Temperature, Stress rupture, Fatigue, MRLife.

INTRODUCTION

The use of polymer matrix composites is constantly increasing due to low cost, low weight and easy processability. These materials are exposed to a large range of environmental and service conditions. Therefore, engineering models are needed to enable the prediction of the mechanical behavior of composite systems.

The main extrinsic parameters (experimental or service conditions) influencing the stiffness of a polymer are strain and deformation state, strain rate and frequency, moisture, time and temperature. In the present paper we will focus on this last parameter. It is well known that the modulus of a polymer can drop dramatically when the material undergoes its glass transition. This change will affect the stiffness of the overall composite. However, it is often assumed that unidirectional composites are “fiber controlled” materials, i.e., if the temperature has no or little effect on the properties of the fibers, the properties of the composite will remain constant in the fiber direction. Recent studies have shown that unidirectional carbon reinforced thermoplastic matrix composites (AS4/PPS) can exhibit a 5% stiffness drop and a 20% strength drop over a 150°C temperature range¹. In the transverse direction, the change in the stiffness of a similar composite in its glassy and rubbery state

would be one order of magnitude (as calculated by a simple rule of mixtures). Therefore the variation of the stiffness of the composite with temperature can not be ignored, even in the axial direction of “fiber-dominated” composites. The basis of the new stiffness-temperature model are summarized in the following section. The integration of the stiffness-temperature model into micromechanical models for polymer matrix materials is illustrated by the case of static end-loaded rupture. Finally, the use of the statistical polymer model in life prediction tools for polymer matrix composites is shown to be possible, and illustrated for the case of fatigue bending.

POLYMER MODULUS VERSUS TEMPERATURE BEHAVIOR MODELING

Most of the literature focuses on the effect of time upon the stiffness of the polymer and does not explicitly relate modulus and temperature. Furthermore, traditional approaches are often limited to a restricted temperature range and to a certain type of polymer^{2,3,4}. A more general approach can be based on the statistics of the polymer secondary bond failure. In order for the material to relax during the different transitions, secondary bonds (Van der Waals, Polar...) need to be broken. Due to the different nature of the bonds and the different distances between atoms, we will observe a distribution of the secondary bond strengths. The rupture of one bond will interact with the failure process of the remaining bonds. Therefore, using Weibull statistics⁵ seems appropriate to describe this process. For each transition, we need to define a characteristic energy, in our case the transition temperature and an associated Weibull coefficient. The equations describing this behavior were derived in detail in a previous study⁶. The present paper focuses on the influence of temperature on PPS-based systems. PPS is a semi-crystalline thermoplastic, with a glass transition varying from 90°C to 120°C depending on the crystallinity content and the molecular weight. This polymer does not exhibit any clear secondary relaxation; therefore, a two-transition equation was used:

$$E = (E_2 - E_3) \exp\left(-\left(\frac{T}{T_2}\right)^{m_2}\right) + E_3 \exp\left(-\left(\frac{T}{T_3}\right)^{m_3}\right) \quad (1)$$

This equation was applied to samples of neat PPS (PPS 0320 PO supplied by Fortron Celanese) with various crystallinity contents (as measured by DSC at 20°C/min⁷): 2% (amorphous sample), 30% (intermediate sample) and 35% (fully crystallized sample). The parameters used in Equation (1) for the different samples are summarized in Table 1. The DMA results at 20Hz and the theoretical data are shown in Figure 1.

Table 1: Parameters used in Equation (1) for the PPS samples

Crystallinity content	2%	30%	35%
T ₂ (glass transition, °C)	97	107	112
T ₃ (melting, °C)	247	257	297
E ₂ (glassy plateau, MPa)	646	832	1348
E ₃ (rubbery plateau, MPa)	3	61	212
m ₂ (glass transition)	60	40	20
m ₃ (flow region)	20	20	20

As expected, the transition temperatures increase with increasing crystallinity content⁸. The height of the glassy plateau increases slightly with increasing crystallinity, and the height of the rubbery plateau increases significantly with an increase in the crystallinity content.

Fig. 1: Experimental and theoretical results for various crystallinities of PPS

The Weibull coefficient associated with the melting transition (m_3) remains constant, and equal to 20. The coefficient associated with the glass transition m_2 was found to vary linearly with crystallinity content (Figure 2) according to Equation (2):

$$m_2 = 62.4 - 0.85T \quad (2)$$

This result is consistent with previous studies of different grades of PEEK and PPS: the m_2 – crystallinity relationship for other grades of PPS reported in the literature was also found to be linear (Figure 2). The two trends are very similar and seem to corroborate a linear variation of m_2 with crystallinity content, independently of the molecular weight of the polymer.

Fig. 2: Variations of m_2 with crystallinity content

The modulus of PPS, with various microstructures, can therefore be represented by Equation (1), based on the statistical representation of the secondary bond breakage. The following sections illustrate the possibility of applying this model to composite materials.

USE IN MICRO AND MACROMECHANICAL MODELS

This explicit relationship between modulus of the polymer and temperature can easily be integrated into micromechanics. To illustrate the feasibility of this approach, the statistical model was used to predict the time-to-failure of unidirectional AS4/PPS samples (amorphous and crystalline) in end-loaded bending for various temperatures and levels of strain. The stress-rupture fixture used in these experiments is shown in Figure 3. Details of the experimental procedure can be found in the literature^{9, 10, 11}.

Fig.3: End-loaded compression bending fixture. From Russel et. al.⁹

Failure under end-loaded bending was found to be compressive and driven by the propagation of a fatal microbuckle¹⁰. From Budiansky¹², and introducing temperature using Equation (1), the following relationship between time-to-failure (t_f) and applied stress can easily be derived^{11,13}:

$$t_f = \frac{1}{M-1} \times \frac{1}{\dot{\gamma}_{ref}} \times \left(\frac{\tau_{ref}(T)}{\sigma(T)} \right)^M \times \left(\frac{1}{\bar{\phi}^{M-1}} - \frac{1}{\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right)^{M-1}} \right) \quad (3)$$

where M is a material constant, τ_{ref} is a reference shear stress, σ is the applied stress and $\bar{\phi}$ is the initial misalignment. Comparison between theoretical predictions and experimental results at 90°C are shown in Figures 4 and 5 for the crystalline and amorphous composite.

All the parameters were calculated using independent experiments and were not readjusted for the present case. Temperature was introduced in Equation (3) via Equation (1). The parameters of Table 1 were used to compute the variations of the polymer stiffness with temperature. The parameters for the low crystallinity and high crystallinity polymers were used in a rule of mixtures in order to compute the stiffness of the amorphous and crystalline composites respectively. The difference observed in the predictions of the time-to-failures of the amorphous and crystalline composites originates from the differences in these parameters (Table 1).

The correlation between experimental data and prediction is very good. The microstructure was taken into consideration: the times-to-failure of the amorphous and crystalline composite were successfully predicted from the properties of the constituents.

Fig.4: Time-to-failure versus maximum strain-to-failure for crystalline AS4/PPS at 90°C

Fig. 5: Time-to-failure versus maximum strain-to-failure for amorphous AS4/PPS at 90°C

The last step was to use this model in order to predict the life of the composite when the thermal loads were combined with cyclic loading. End-loaded fatigue experiments were performed. A cyclic compression load varying from 0 to a maximum load (corresponding to

a maximum strain at the specimen mid-length) was applied to the specimen. The experiments were performed at various temperatures. The life of the composite was recorded as a function of the maximum applied strain. Details of the experimental procedure can be found in the literature¹⁴. The MRLife approach was used in order to combine stress rupture and fatigue^{15,14}: the continuity function ψ can be related to the failure function Fa (strain over ultimate strain-to-failure in the present case):

$$\psi = 1 - Fa \quad (4)$$

Assuming a general kinetic law:

$$\frac{d\psi}{d\tau} = \psi j \tau^{j-1} \quad (5)$$

where j is a material parameter and

$$\tau = \frac{t}{\hat{\tau}} \quad (6)$$

$\hat{\tau}$ is a characteristic time, and after some mathematical manipulation the remaining strength can be expressed by the following integral:

$$Fr = 1 - \int_0^{\tau} (1 - Fa(\tau)) j \tau^{j-1} d\tau \quad (7)$$

The j parameter can be measured via remaining strength experiments¹⁴ and was found equal to 0.66 in the present case. Global failure of the specimen occurs when the remaining strength becomes equal to the failure function. Therefore, combining Equation (3) and (7), the life of the composite under cyclic load can be calculated. The temperature dependency was introduced via Equations (1) and (3). The results of this approach are shown at 90°C in Figure 6.

Fig.6: Bending fatigue at 90°C, experimental data and predicted values

The prediction fits the experimental data very well. Once again, no coefficients were adjusted in order to predict the life of the composite under combined thermal and bending loads

CONCLUSIONS

The statistical concept developed in the present study has been successful in describing the variations of the stiffness of PPS with temperature, from the glassy state to the flow of the polymer, and within the property transition regions. End-loaded bending stress rupture was chosen to illustrate the potential of the polymer model to the use in micromechanics of polymer matrix composites. Finally the model was successfully used in MRLife to predict the life of unidirectional AS4/PPS composites in fatigue bending at elevated temperatures. This example illustrates the powerful potential of the model in introducing explicit temperature-dependency in life prediction tools for composites.

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